

Potential Local Anesthetics: Synthesis of Substituted Benzyloxy-Phenyl-Oxamates and their Derivatives

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In order to evaluate their anesthetic and anticonvulsant properties, various benzyloxy oxamides have been synthesized.

AMONG several basic amides known, α -diethyl-amino 2,6-dimethyl acetanilide (Xylocaine) is the most potent as local anesthetic¹. Dalal and Trivedi² and Patel and Trivedi³ have synthesized several acetamides and propionamides which show activity as compared to xylocaine. Some α -sec-amino-N-(α -Aryl alkyl) acetamides show two to four fold activity of xylocaine⁴.

Trivedi and Shah⁵ have shown that benzyloxy acetanilides and propionamides are also very effective. Several basic esters of aryloxy and aralkyloxy carboxylic acids containing phenyl, benzyl and phenethyl group are also good anesthetics⁶, these were among the first to show activity in a molecule which contained oxanilic moiety.

The present work was undertaken with a view to synthesize basic amides containing oxanilic acid moiety to evaluate their anesthetic and anticonvulsant properties.

Benzyloxy acetanilides were prepared by treating benzyl halides with the appropriate acetaminophenol under alkaline condition⁷. These were then hydrolysed to benzyloxy anilines (I) by refluxing with KOH⁸. When (I) reacted with diethyl oxalate⁹, Ethyl-N-(4-substituted-benzyloxy)-phenyl oxamates (II) were formed. (II) when reacted with a secondary amine R'R''NH gave N-sec-Amino (4-substituted-benzyloxy)-phenyl oxamide (III). The latter were converted into their hydrochlorides for testing their local anesthetic and C.N.S. effects. None of these compounds shows promising activity.

Scheme of Synthesis

Experimental

Ethyl-N-p-substituted benzyloxy-phenyl-oxamates (II)

To a stirred solution of *p*-substituted benzyloxy-anilines (0.12M) in 150 ml absolute EtOH, distilled diethyl oxalate (38 ml : 0.25M) was added at room temperature, after 24 hrs, the reaction mixture was filtered to remove a small amount of diamide and ethanol from the filtrate by distillation. Unreacted diethyl oxalate was then removed by distillation under the low pressure, the residue was washed with 10 ml EtOH, and allowed to crystallize. These were recrystallized in absolute ethanol using animal charcoal. Average yield 90%. The other oxamates prepared by this method are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ETHYL-N-SUBSTITUTED BENZYLOXY-PHENYL-OXAMATES(II)

Sr. No.	Y	M.P. of the substance	Molecular formula	% of Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	98	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₄	4.68	4.66
2.	CH ₃	118	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₄	4.47	4.44
3.	Cl	126	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₄ Cl	4.19	4.16
4.	Br	100	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₄ Br	3.70	3.66
5.	OCH ₃	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₅	4.25	4.22

TABLE 2—*N*-*sec*-AMINO-(4-SUBSTITUTED-BENZYLOXY)-PHENYL-OXAMIDE HYDROCHLORIDE (III)

Sr. No.	<i>γ</i> -para	Sec. Base HNR'R''	Mol. Formula	M.P. Base	M.P. of HCl	% of Nitrogen	
						Calc.	Found (Base)
1.	H	Morpholine	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	108	216	8.23	8.20
2.	CH ₃	Morpholine	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	101	157	7.91	7.88
3.	Cl	Morpholine	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	88	161	7.47	7.44
4.	Br	Morpholine	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ Br	125	158	6.68	6.62
5.	H	Piperidine	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	116	226	8.28	8.21
6.	CH ₃	Piperidine	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	110	221	7.95	7.91
7.	Cl	Piperidine	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	80	185	7.52	7.49
8.	Br	Piperidine	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Br	132	198	6.72	6.70
9.	H	Diethylamine	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	141	230	8.59	8.56
10.	CH ₃	Diethylamine	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	118	122	8.23	8.20
11.	Cl	Diethylamine	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	82	210	7.77	7.74
12.	Br	Diethylamine	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Br	138	186	6.91	6.89
13.	H	Piperazine	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃	132	210	12.39	12.37
14.	CH ₃	Piperazine	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃	107	180	11.90	11.86
15.	Cl	Piperazine	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	76	177	11.24	11.21
16.	Br	Piperazine	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	140	226	10.05	9.98

N-*sec*-Amino-(4-substituted benzyloxy)-phenyl-oxamide hydrochloride (III)

A mixture of the above benzyloxy oxamates (0.01 *M*) and secondary amine (0.02*M*) in absolute EtOH (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 hrs. Alcohol was distilled off. The residue was poured into 400 ml water at 0°. Solids were separated, filtered, dried, and crystallized from absolute EtOH, liquids were extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and dry hydrogen chloride gas passed into the ethereal solution. The insoluble hydrochloride separated were crystallized from absolute alcohol. These compounds are listed in Table 2.

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